

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE .

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ANNOTATION.

R^3 get acquainted with the skills of drawing straight lines and planes in space. Placing points in space. To find the distances from a point to a straight line and a plane in space and to be able to describe them. Find the distance between parallel planes and describe them.

Key words : Space, straight line, planes, plane intersection

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it be given by the parametric equations of the straight line and the general equation of the plane Π in the Cartesian plane :

$$u : \begin{cases} x = x_0 + lt, \\ y = y_0 + mt, \\ z = z_0 + nt, \end{cases} \quad \vec{u}(l, m, n), (1)$$

$$\Pi : Ax + By + Cz + D = 0 \quad \vec{n}(A, B, C). (2)$$

First of all, let's dwell on the problem of finding the point of intersection of a straight line and a plane: for this, the given equations should be considered as a system. From (8) and (9).

$$Ax_0 + By_0 + Cz_0 + D + t(Al + Bm + Cn) = 0. \quad (3)$$

$Al + Bm + Cn \neq 0$ provided

$$t = -\frac{Ax_0 + By_0 + Cz_0 + D}{Al + Bm + Cn} (4)$$

will be If we put this value of t in (8), the sought point is found. But

$$Al + Bm + Cn = 0 \quad (5)$$

if the condition is met, that is $\vec{u} \perp \vec{n}$ is parallel to the straight line . Π Vice versa, $u // \Pi \Rightarrow \vec{u} \perp \vec{n} \Rightarrow \vec{u} \cdot \vec{n} = 0$.

So, $\vec{u} \cdot \vec{n} = Al + Bm + Cn = 0$ the condition indicates the parallelism of a straight line and a plane.

$$u \perp \Pi \Rightarrow \vec{u} \parallel \vec{n} \Rightarrow \frac{l}{A} = \frac{m}{B} = \frac{n}{C}, (6)$$

this condition (12) means that the straight line is perpendicular to the plane.

$u \in \Pi$ is a special case of the interaction of a straight line and a plane. At this time, the condition (11') should be fulfilled and it should be excluded $M_0 \in \Pi$, i.e

$$Ax_0 + By_0 + Cz_0 + D = 0. (7)$$

Hence, $u \subset \Pi \Leftrightarrow (11'), (13)$.

Now we give the formula for finding the angle between a straight line and a plane.

1 - drawing

Description. The angle between a straight line and a plane is the angle between a straight line and its orthogonal projection on this plane (Figure 1). We

$0 \leq \varphi \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$ assume that.

It can be seen from the diagram φ 1 that instead of $(\vec{n}, \vec{u})$ angle is acceptable.

This angle is equal $\frac{\pi}{2} - \varphi$ to or $\frac{\pi}{2} + \varphi$. Hence, $\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \varphi\right) = \sin \varphi$,

$\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \varphi\right) = -\sin \varphi$, therefore

$$\sin \varphi = |\cos(\vec{n}, \vec{u})| = \frac{|Al + Bm + Cn|}{\sqrt{A^2 + B^2 + C^2} \cdot \sqrt{l^2 + m^2 + n^2}}. (8)$$

examples . _ a) This

$$\begin{cases} x = 1 + 2t, \\ y = 3t, \\ z = -2 + t \end{cases}$$

find the point of intersection of the plane with the straight line .
 $2x - y + z + 1 = 0$

Solving . In the equations of the straight line x, y, z we put the values of into the equation of the plane:

$$2(1 + 2t) - 3t + (-2 + t) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad t = \frac{1}{2}.$$

$$\text{In that case } x = 1 + 2\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = 0, \quad y = -\frac{3}{2}, \quad z = -2 - \frac{1}{2} = -\frac{5}{2};;$$

the sought point $\left(0, -\frac{3}{2}, -\frac{5}{2}\right)$.

b) Find the distance from the point R (7, 9, 7) to the straight line.

$$\frac{x-2}{4} = \frac{y-1}{3} = \frac{z}{2}$$

Solving. We have not given a formula for finding the distance from a point to a straight line, such a problem is easily solved as follows:

a) the equation of a plane perpendicular to the given straight line passing through the given point is drawn;

b) the point of intersection of the given straight line with this plane is found;

c) the distance between this found point and the given point is found.

In this regard, we will begin to solve the problem.

the equation of the line perpendicular to the vector from the point P(7,9,7)

$$\vec{n} = \vec{u}(4,3,2): 4(x-7) + 3(y-9) + 2(z-7) = 0 \text{ or}$$

$$4x + 3y + 2z - 69 = 0 (*)$$

b) we write the equation of the given diagonal line in parametric form : and $x = 2 + 4t, \quad y = (1 + 3t), \quad z = 2t$ add these (*) to the equation :

$$4(2 + 4t) + 3(1 + 3t) + 2 \cdot 2t - 69 = 0,$$

$$29t - 58 = 0,$$

$$t = 2$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} x = 2 + 4 \cdot 2 = 10, \\ y = 1 + 3 \cdot 2 = 7, \\ z = 2 \cdot 2 = 4 \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow Q(10, 7, 4) \text{ of intersection of a line with a straight line .}$$

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